

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON IMPROVING COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF NON-PHILOLOGICAL EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract. World integration has led to the formation of a fundamentally new sociocultural space, in which interpersonal and interethnic communication occupies a special place. The new social order of society has changed the status of a foreign language as an academic discipline. The main goal of the training was to master the English language as a means of oral and written communication in various spheres of social and professional activity in the context of intercultural communication.

Keywords: communication skills, education, English, competence.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of a non-linguistic educational institution, it is quite difficult to implement the above-mentioned approach. Analysis of curricula, as well as performance results in the subject “English. Professional vocabulary” in the educational institution “Higher State College of Communications” allows us to identify some problems in the development of communication skills among students. This educational institution trains non-philological students who, in a short period of time with a minimum number of hours (from 2 to 4 hours per week), as well as with a rich program in specialized subjects, must master the necessary communication skills and a large stock of professional vocabulary for understanding text read or heard. In addition to the above-mentioned productive and receptive skills, students must have others, for example, summarizing the material they have read, discussing it in an oral conversation, and conducting a discussion within a given topic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Analysis of oral and written responses showed that the greatest difficulty is the process of speaking a foreign language and the further use of the studied material in oral and written speech. In our work to develop students’ communication skills in

foreign language classes, we took into account both the modern experience of domestic and foreign schools, as well as the many years of experience accumulated by generations of teachers.

Many scientific teams and methodologists were involved in the development of the communicative direction: A.A. Leontyeva, G.A. Kitaygorodskaya, V.L. Skalkina, I.A. Zimnyaya, R. Allwright, S. Savignon, etc. [1-7]. Undoubtedly, the approach of each scientist is of great value, but we would like to draw attention to the characteristics of the communicative method.

The communicative technique assumes that the unit of communication is a speech act as a means of conveying speech intentions using language.

According to scientists, modern principles of teaching and learning foreign languages in non-philological universities are aimed at understanding linguistic intercultural characteristics along with a focus on understanding the sociocultural content, the textual nature of communication, which not only supports, but also activates the student's interest in learning a foreign language [1].

The purpose of the article is to consider the possibilities of teaching communication to students of engineering universities with an emphasis on teaching professional communication as a component of teaching intercultural communication in a foreign language.

With the change in the development priorities of modern education, the expansion of the cultural approach to teaching, the growing interest in international cooperation and the expansion of its capabilities, the sociocultural component plays an increasingly important role in teaching a foreign language. The sociocultural component in teaching a professional foreign language is based on the established sociocultural competence of students, which was formed at school in classes in history, geography, literature, as a result of studying the government system, general culture and speech etiquette of the country of the language being studied. The method of teaching English in the professional direction of students of non-philological specialties is aimed at exploring the problems associated with studying a foreign language not only as a compulsory and interesting university discipline, but also as one of the ways to obtain professional knowledge in the specialty chosen by the student. Thanks to interest in foreign languages, the attention of linguists and methodologists has shifted from studying the characteristics of the literary language to the study of the language used in real communication between specialists in

certain fields. Therefore, there was a need to create an English language course separately for doctors, engineers, IT, etc. Modern advances in the field of methods of teaching foreign languages for special purposes have led to the conclusion: since a foreign language is used differently in communication situations between specialists of different professions, having determined the features of typical communication situations between specialists in each specific industry, it is possible to model the process of their real communication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Let us highlight the basic principles of the communicative approach [2]:

- principle of functionality;
- the principle of situationality (students have a need to discuss problem situations, which means their motivation to learn increases);
- the principle of individualization.
- Training according to this methodology occurs in the following stages:
 - introduction of new speech utterances (perception of them by ear);
 - explanation of their functions in speech (with the help of context - texts, dialogues), memorization of speech cliches;
 - the use of speech utterances in similar speech situations – automation of skills occurs;
 - transfer of skills to new situations.

The peculiarity of this method is that it includes two approaches:

- intuitive approach – in the first stages, which allows you to quickly remember statements;
- conscious approach – at the last stages of learning, where there is a conscious choice of one or another statement depending on the communicative purpose of the task.

However, it should be noted that the communicative technique has its advantages and disadvantages. The difference between the communicative method and other methods is that repetition and memorization are not used here, but an open-ended conversation is conducted. Oral speech in communicative lessons significantly prevails over reading and writing.

Some teachers have recently been engaged in quite a lot of debate on the issue of whether it is worth correcting mistakes in the speech of their students and how to do it correctly. The opinions of teachers were divided on three fronts. Some people

believe that there is no need to correct mistakes. The main thing is that students talk a lot and quickly and have the opportunity to express themselves. Others say that basic errors still need to be corrected. Still others, whose numbers are steadily growing, are of the opinion that you need to learn to speak correctly, and not somehow [3].

Also, the weak link of the communicative method is the study of grammar. Many people believe that grammar will be learned on its own, that is, it is not worth studying it specifically. However, it is not. Studying grammar in the communicative teaching method should occupy 30% of the teaching time. Penny Er believes that in the future the communicative method will also occupy a leading position among other methods of learning foreign languages. However, all the shortcomings that have been identified in its development to date will be taken into account and corrected. That is, the language will be learned not just to survive in a foreign country, but for high-quality international communication. And for this to be realized, it is necessary to establish a balance between communicative and traditional methods of language learning.

Over the years, each teacher develops his own style of conducting classes and communicating with students. The teacher accumulates techniques that allow him to diversify classes, increase interest in them, bring humor and lively discussion into the classroom, and help maintain sustainable interest in the subject. Students should constantly feel that the teacher wants to teach them and knows how to do it, therefore the personality of the teacher, his attitude towards his subject and students plays a very important role in teaching a foreign language. If the personal interests of the teacher coincide with the professional interests of the students, we can assume that such students will achieve significant success in mastering professional English.

Issues of formation of foreign language sociocultural competence in the 21st century. studied by R.A. Grishkova, L.I. Morskaya, A.B. Tarnopolsky, V.M. Topalova, foreign scientists L. Bredella, V. Hollett, T. Hutchinson and others. In most publications on the topic, the authors agree with that that the formation of foreign language sociocultural competence of students of non-philological specialties is necessary. P.S. Robbinson, E. Taron, G. Yul made a great contribution to the development of methods of teaching English in a professional direction (ESP - English for Specific Purposes), however, as A.B. Tarnopolsky emphasizes, there are certain disagreements in teaching English language for special purposes in the

West and in our country. They lie in the fact that in our higher education system, teaching a foreign language for special purposes takes place on the basis of programs, curricula and materials compiled by linguists and methodologists (of course, with the involvement of specialists in the relevant field). The purpose, content and methods of teaching are formulated centrally, and then transferred to the classroom along with prepared educational materials, so that students have practically no choice what to learn, when to learn, for what, using what materials [4]. Often, learning a foreign language ends in the 2nd year, that is, precisely when it is still too early to talk about the language of professional communication, and all attention is focused (and correctly) on mastering the common language, its rules, system, and basic vocabulary. English-speaking countries take the opposite approach. Western methodology, as its leading postulate, requires that teaching English for specific purposes (ESP) begin with an analysis of the needs of students of each specific group. Only on the basis of such an analysis should the teacher working in this group himself create a program and curriculum for it. This approach is most consistent with the requirements of the Common European Recommendations for Language Education, which propose that when teaching foreign languages, we should proceed from the needs, motives, characteristics and abilities of students. So, at this stage of development of domestic pedagogical science, the process of teaching a foreign language for professional communication and highlighting in this process the formation of foreign language sociocultural competence requires significant changes and improvement.

CONCLUSION

Analyzing the content of teaching English in a professional direction, we have to conclude that the most advisable thing is to make language learning continuous, and then in the third and fourth year it is possible to identify common topics that are studied by all students in a professional foreign language course and combine them into one business language course, common to all specialties. Students of all specialties must study material related to international activities: international funds, foreign companies, banks, international human rights organizations, services, cooperation with foreign partners, etc. Students should be taught how to prepare for interviews for employment with a foreign company, write business letters, communicate verbally with possible foreign partners, prepare and give presentations, organize negotiations, fill out relevant documents, draw up business

plans, resumes, reports, etc. Stories from students who returned from internships in foreign countries indicate that knowledge of the sociocultural differences of different peoples is indeed very important, since without knowledge of behavioral skills or etiquette norms accepted, for example, in the UK, Germany, Poland or the USA, interaction and cooperation can fail or fail to bring the desired results, which otherwise could be achieved even at the level of friendship and desire for mutual assistance. As for professional vocabulary in the specialty, its use is narrow and focused, therefore, to master it, a large number of specialized textbooks, for example, from Cambridge University Press, can be used.

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